

Vilmos Peschka (1929–2006)

A member of the Editorial Board of *Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie* since 1978 and one of the founders and the first president of IVR-Hungary, Professor Vilmos Peschka died on 25 July 2006 at his hearted resort place, of an increasingly growing importance in his personal life in the last decades, at Balatonszabadi, on the estate of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

Born on 17 December 1929, he had grown up in Óbuda [Old Buda] and took baccalaureate in a school where his English teacher happened to be a famous avant-garde writer freshly withdrawn into intellectual exile from the communist push, Miklós Szentkuthy, to whom the pupils were expected to perform Ovidius in Latin and Shakespeare in English. Later on, in the metropolitan Eötvös Loránd University, he had become the student of Imre Szabó, the number one representative of Sovietised Marxism on the domain of law in Hungary, who remained his mentor and helping hand until and well after Peschka himself arrived in. Notably, Szabó selected him both as a postgraduate student in 1954 and as a research fellow at the Institute for Legal Studies of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences in 1957, and, within two decades of outstanding accomplishment, proposed him – successfully – to be elected as a corresponding, respectively ordinary, member of the Academy of Sciences in 1976, resp. 1982. By a most fortunate combination and certainly also owing to his friendship with civilists – arching from the influential Marxist Gyula Eörsi to the international privatist Ferenc Mádl – , he also joined to the Civil law department staff of his one-time *alma mater*, himself becoming a professor of civil law later on, to help in students' practicum by teaching them how to solve civil law cases. Half a decade ago from now, Mádl, then President of the Republic, awarded him Széchenyi-prize, the highest prize in Hungary for intellectual (scholarly) achievement.

Vilmos Peschka was all through devoted to thorough studies of foundational – mostly philosophical and methodological – issues underlying philosophising in and on law. He dedicated most of his research efforts to monographic treatments. The papers he published at all – in sequence of frequency, in *Acta Juridica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* (since his editorship-in-chief, *Acta Juridica Hungarica*), *Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie*, *Rechtstheorie*, and *Archives de Philosophie du Droit* – were either occasional in exception or, mostly, pre-published chapters. Everything he prepared was hand-written almost with no correction, dictated to his preferred typist and subsequently finalised without the slightest modification.

Under the rule of Socialism' Marxism as a quasi devotional substitution and almost for the entire era officially represented by Szabó's legal theorising, Peschka set the standard of quality and demands for the philosophical approach in the theoretical understanding of law. If not Marxist, he would have been a conceptual analyst. For him, law was a most serious national game standing for some far-away social abstraction rather than a harsh reality, changing and multi-faceted in its diverse civilisational forms. This is why he worked from Marx, Engels, Hegel, Lukács, Weber and Kelsen and other neo-Kantians (with Thomas Mann and cold detachment in the background), that is, almost exclusively from philosophical treatments, having no particular regard to or interest in either academic journals reporting on past or present factual developments or anything beyond the reach of an already formed conceptual world. For instance, he never came close in person to either historico-comparative treatments or ones relating to the reality or power aspect of the law. His own conceptualisation was sharp and categorical, final in and for the oeuvre. He, the sporting man, took scholarship equally seriously. In theoretical building, what mattered for him was exclusively wherefrom and which way, instead of whereto to conclude. This is why he was ready to fight against any occasional or theoretically veiled political and ideological interference with scholarship. On the other hand and perhaps also in counterbalance, the categorial realm he designed was bound to remain an abstract world, by far not spirited by his adored Goethe's greenness of life.

As to his oeuvre, the meticulous processing of the Basic issues of a theory on legal relations (*A jogviszonyelmélet alapvet kérdései*, 1960, serving as his first, academic "candidate" thesis) was followed by a rather lengthy conceptual development on the Sources of law and law-making (*Jogforrás és jogalkotás*, 1965), in which he inferred from the categorial building he framed up to the smallest details that, running counter to the dogma of legal policy in force in all "actually existing socialisms" since the time Vishinsky's Stalinism had prevailed, at least the so called guiding decisions of the supreme courts in the socialist orbit are acts of partly making (and not merely applying) the law, so only their elevation to the official rank of being a "source of the law" themselves could be justified. His outstanding overview on *Grundprobleme der modernen Rechtsphilosophie* (Budapest, Akadémiai Kiadó, 1974) – also in Japanese: *Gendai hōtetsugaku no kihonmondai* trans. Ameya Wafu (Tōkyō, Hōritsu Bunkasha, 1981) – became a classic in the socialist world by its open-minded surveying the main trends of legal philosophising characteristic of 20th century and especially its post-war periods, a master mind for a while, for the rigorously Marxist, albeit quite emphatic criticism he exerted in his series of theoretical confrontations. Such an assessment of the western intellectual legacy, widened to critically confront even more directions and issues, was done by outlining the theoretical perspective of Weber's sociology of law with special regard to the categories it had implied as parts of one unified doctrine (*Max Weber jogszociológiája*, 1975) and a number of papers on the historical roots (spanning from Hegel and Savigny up to phenomenologism) and foundational topics of philosophising in law as well as its extension to the philosophical bases of private law (reflecting upon interpretation of legal act and gaps in law as well) (collected in his *Jog és jogfilozófia*, 1980). An interlude followed, by explaining the grounds of law and legal theorising in the light of ethics (*Az etika vonzásában*, 1980), mostly on quite an abstract philosophical plane, reconsidering Aristotle, Kant and neo-Kantians, only to arrive at some conclusions for a prospected legal ontology. After George Lukács had released the basics of his *Zur Ontologie des gesellschaftlichen Seins*, the challenge to transform the officially labelled "Marxist theory of law" into a modern legal ontology became imminent, at least in Hungary. Peschka faced it, first of all by elaborating his theory of legal norms – *Die*

Theorie der Rechtsnormen (Budapest, Akadémiai Kiadó, 1982) – , revolving around the understanding of norms in terms of causality and teleology, their explanation as “the particular reflection of objective reality”, and complemented to by a series of detailed analyses of their factual and axiological contents as well as of the conditions, extension and quality of their validity. *Nolent, volent*, it was two decades ago from now on already that, as we can realise it recently, he summed up his legal philosophising in a synthetical re-assessment – *Die Eigenartigkeit des Rechts* (Budapest, Akadémiai Kiadó, 1989) – in which, with also sensible reading of Hartmann and Larenz involved, the foundational issues of the chances and very conceivability of ontologising in and on law, the nature of the law’s social embeddedness, the “legal reflection” of reality as well as the “law as objectification” issue were contemplated. This final oeuvre on the peculiarity of law became subsequently partly crowned, partly annexed by some late papers (collected in his *Appendix »A jog sajátosságaihoz«*, 1992), reconsidering Hayek’s position and Kelsen’s posthumous theory of legal norms and, by having drawn especially from the study of Fikentscher, Gadamer and Kaufmann, opening its theorising wide up to the merge of his own philosophical outlook’s self-dissolution in the closing papers, in which he tried to integrate in his own philosophical system both the problematic of the case-norm and the theoretical acceptability of hermeneutic moments in the very philosophical reconstruction of law.

Its main source of inspiration notwithstanding, his entire undertaking was devised from the early 1970s on to break up the Socialism’s Marxism artificially erected cold-war-type self-closure in order to build on, as a common scholarly heritage, Weber and Kelsen, by opening the gates for a professional discourse, in the name of theorising out of touch of any partisanship or corruption, between the West and the Sovietised-Marxised East.

Some in Hungary praise his oeuvre as unprecedentedly original and novative, displaying most of the traits of a trend of its own in the history of legal philosophising ever done in Hungary (practically cultivated from the last third of the 19th century on). Others regard it rather as an achievement at a rather high level indeed, that could at all be evolved out of the limiting political and intellectual conditions of the era, and, as such, the best the Hungarian legal thought could at all produce during at least three decades starting from the 1960s in Hungary.

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